

Vehicle Detection Method Based on ADE-YOLOV3 Algorithm

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Abstract: Aiming at the problem of repeated detection of YOLOV3 algorithm in vehicle detection, the ADE-YOLOV3 vehicle detection algorithm is proposed. The algorithm uses K-means clustering algorithm to determine the number of target candidate frames and aspect ratio according to the inherent width and height characteristics of the vehicle. Then, according to the results obtained by clustering, the anchor parameters are reset, which makes the ADE-YOLOV3 network have certain pertinence in vehicle detection. Finally, the migration learning method is used to improve the network structure, and the optimal weight model is obtained, which improves the training precision of the model. The experimental results show that compared with the original YOLOV3 method, the mAP is increased from 91.4% to 95%, the repeated detection rate is reduced from 5.6% to 2.1%, and the detection speed by 50fps. The detection accuracy is improved and the problem of repeated detection is effectively avoided.

Keywords: Vehicle Detection; Deep Learning; YOLOv3; K-means; Migration Learning

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, with the continuous advancement of urbanization and the increase of road vehicles, the detection and identification of moving vehicles in traffic video or images is an important task of traffic management, and it is of great significance for improving traffic safety. Vehicle detection and recognition is a branch of target detection. In this field, it is mainly divided into traditional target detection algorithm and deep learning-based target detection algorithm.

In the traditional target detection algorithm, the commonly used methods are direction gradient histogram [1], scale invariant feature transform algorithm [2], local binary mode [3] and so on. Most of the methods used in these methods are support vector machine classifiers [4], but they are too dependent on researchers in the process of extracting features. Different features need to be designed according to different goals. If the feature extraction is unreasonable, it will have a big impact on the accuracy of the final vehicle detection.

In recent years, convolutional neural networks have made breakthroughs in image segmentation, target detection, target classification, and image interpretation [5-9]. A large number of deep learning-based target detection algorithms have surpassed traditional detection methods and become a new and widely used detection method. According to the idea of algorithm design, these methods can be divided into two types, one is the target detection algorithm based on regional nomination, and the other is the target detection algorithm based on end-to-end learning. The detection algorithms based on regional nomination mainly include R-CNN [10], Fast R-CNN [11], Faster R-CNN [12] and so on. In detail, the R-CNN uses a selective search algorithm to extract candidate regions from the picture, and the target detection accuracy is greatly improved compared with the conventional method, but the number of candidate frames is large, resulting in low efficiency. Based on R-CNN, Fast R-CNN avoids many redundant feature extraction operations in R-CNN and improves the accuracy of target recognition. Faster R-CNN further improves the speed by constructing a regional suggestion network to extract

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candidate frames instead of using a selective search algorithm with high time overhead. Target detection algorithms based on end-to-end learning mainly include YOLO [13], SSD [14], YOLOV2 [15], and YOLOV3 [16]. YOLO does not need to extract the candidate area in advance, and integrates the target boundary frame position coordinate prediction and category prediction, and the running speed is greatly improved, but the YOLO object positioning difference is large and the precision is not high. SSD uses VGG-16[17] as the feature extraction network, and draws on the similar RPN network of Faster R-CNN, but it differs in that the classification and border regression are performed after using the regional suggestion network on multiple feature maps of CNN. SSD is very effective for large target detection, but it is not good for small target detection. YOLOv2 has made a series of improvements on the basis of YOLO, and the target detection accuracy and speed have been improved, but the feature extraction network of YOLOV2 is relatively simple, and the recognition performance of the occluded target is not good enough.

YOLOV3 has added the idea of deep residual neural network [18].The output of the traditional neural network n-1 layer can only be used as input to the n-layer. The deep residual neural network breaks it, so that the output of a layer can directly cross several layers as the input of a later layer,which makes the feature extraction network more complex and multi-scale feature prediction. It has obtained the best balance between detection speed and accuracy, and has become the preferred target detection in engineering. One of the algorithms. However, when YOLOV3 detects vehicle targets, there is a problem of repeated detection. In order to improve the practicality and accuracy of the YOLOV3 algorithm in vehicle detection and reduce the probability of repeated detection, this paper improves the YOLOV3 and proposes the ADE-YOLOV3 vehicle detection algorithm. Firstly, for vehicle detection, due to the unreasonable design of the original anxiety parameter of the original YOLOV3 algorithm, this paper re-clustering and calculating the anchor parameter on its own dataset to improve the detection rate of the bounding box. The improved anchor parameter is more specific to the vehicle data and improves the training accuracy of the model. Then, using migration learning to help the new model training, while modifying part of the network structure, making full use of more rich details for feature fusion, making the model training better.

II. YOLOV3 PRINCIPLE

A. Feature Extraction Network Darknet-53

YOLOV3 does not use YOLOV2's Darknet-19 for feature extraction, but instead uses a new network structure called Darknet-53. The network structure draws on the idea of residual network, uses a lot of residual hopping links, and continuously uses 3×3 and 1×1 convolutional layers, and 3×3 convolutional layers for increasing dimensions, 1×1 convolutional layer is used to compress the 3x3 convolutional feature representation, and finally the normalization operation is added after each convolutional layer to prevent network overfitting. Its network structure is shown in Figure 1.

	Type	Filters	Size	Output
	Convolutional	32	3 × 3	256 × 256
	Convolutional	64	3 × 3 / 2	128 × 128
1x	Convolutional	32	1 × 1	
	Convolutional	64	3 × 3	
	Residual			128 × 128
	Convolutional	128	3 × 3 / 2	64 × 64
2x	Convolutional	64	1 × 1	
	Convolutional	128	3 × 3	
	Residual			64 × 64
	Convolutional	256	3 × 3 / 2	32 × 32
8x	Convolutional	128	1 × 1	
	Convolutional	256	3 × 3	
	Residual			32 × 32
	Convolutional	512	3 × 3 / 2	16 × 16
8x	Convolutional	256	1 × 1	
	Convolutional	512	3 × 3	
	Residual			16 × 16
	Convolutional	1024	3 × 3 / 2	8 × 8
4x	Convolutional	512	1 × 1	
	Convolutional	1024	3 × 3	
	Residual			8 × 8
	Avgpool		Global	
	Connected		1000	
	Softmax			

Figure 1 : Darknet-53 network structure

The network is faster and more powerful than the Darknet-19, ResNet-152 and ResNet-101. The characteristic network performance pairs under the ImageNet data set are shown in Table 1

Table 1 : Network performance comparison table

Backbone	Top-1/%	Top-5/%	Bn Ops	BFL OP/s	FPS
DarkNet-19	74.1	91.8	7.29	1246	171
ResNet-101	77.1	93.7	19.7	1039	53

ResNet-152	77.6	93.8	29.4	1090	37
DarkNet-53	77.2	93.8	18.7	1457	78

B. Analysis of YOLOV3 Design Ideas and Advantages and Disadvantages

YOLOV3 uses multi-scale feature fusion strategy for feature detection. The scales of the three feature maps are 13×13, 26×26, and 52×52, which improves the detection accuracy of small targets.

Like the YOLOV2, YOLOV3 uses the K-means algorithm to perform dimensional clustering on the targets in the dataset, and then distributes the a priori frames obtained by clustering equally to three scales, and applies the larger first on the smallest 13×13 feature map. The frame (116×90), (156×198), (373×326) is suitable for detecting large objects. The medium 26×26 feature map uses a medium a priori box (30×61), (62×45), (59×119), suitable for detecting medium-sized objects. Smaller a priori boxes (10×13), (16×30), (33×23) are applied to the larger 52×52 feature map, which is suitable for detecting smaller objects.

YOLOV3 uses the sigmoid classifier instead of the Softmax classifier, while the loss function uses binary cross-entropy loss during training. Based on the above design ideas, the detection speed of YOLOV3 has made great progress compared with other detection algorithms, and its background false detection rate is low and versatility is stronger. However, the a priori box parameters adopted by YOLOV3 are obtained by using K-means algorithm in advance clustering. In the actual target location identification process, the problems of missed detection, false detection and repeated detection may occur. The performance of the YOLOV3 algorithm and other algorithms are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Performance comparison between YOLOV3 and other algorithms

Method	mAP-50%	Times/ms
SSD	45.4	61
R-FCN	46.1	85
RetinaNet-50-500	50.9	73
RetinaNet-101-500	53.1	90
RetinaNet-50-800	57.5	198
YOLOV3-320	51.5	22
YOLOV3-416	55.3	29
YOLOV3-608	57.9	51

III. IMPROVED ADE-YOLOV3 ALGORITHM

A. ADE-YOLOV3 Algorithm Network Parameter Optimization

The YOLOV3 algorithm draws on the anchor mechanism in the fast R-CNN RPN, but instead of manually setting the anchor parameter, the dimension clustering method is used to determine the value of the anchor parameter, which is (10, 13), (16, 30), (33, 23), (30, 61), (62, 45), (59, 119), (116, 90), (156, 198), (373, 326). Each value consists of two numbers, one for height and one for width. In the process of target detection, the parameter setting of the a priori frame has a great influence on the accuracy of the training result. Therefore, it is very important to set the a priori box parameters according to the inherent shape of the vehicle when detecting the vehicle. In order to obtain the optimal anchor parameter value, ADE-YOLOV3 uses K-means clustering algorithm to cluster the target frame of the self-marked dataset in the self-made dataset, and obtain the optimal number of anchors and width and height dimensions as the network parameters of the ADE-YOLOV3 algorithm.

In determining the parameters, if the distance metric uses a standard Euclidean distance, a large a priori box will produce more errors than a small a priori box. Therefore, in order to reduce the error caused by the size of the a priori frame itself, ADE-YOLOV3 replaces the original Euclidean distance with the intersection ratio of the target frame and the a priori frame of the vehicle label as the objective function, and the smaller the value of the objective function, the better the clustering effect. The calculation formula of the objective function S is:

$$D = \min \sum_{box=0}^n \sum_{cen=0}^k [1 - IOU] \quad (1)$$

In the formula, box represents the target box, cen is the cluster center, n is the number of samples, and k is the number of categories. Using this method on the homemade data the relationship between S and k is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: S line diagram of change with K

It can be seen from Fig 2 that with the increase of the K value, the objective function value is gradually reduced, and the clustering effect is getting better and better. According to the idea of the elbow method, we select the clustering result at k=9 as an improved algorithm. The parameters, the results of the clustering are (45, 55), (118, 154), (33, 60), (18, 23), (36, 27), (21, 32), (273, 376), (69, 90), (28, 43), the clustering results are more targeted than the original parameters. Therefore, the improved anchor parameters are used instead of the original parameters for training and testing.

B. ADE-YOLOV3 Algorithm Network Structure Optimization

The YOLOV3 algorithm uses the Darknet-53 network to greatly improve the network feature extraction capability and solve the problem of feature degradation caused by increasing the network depth. When the number of layers of the network increases, the features extracted by the network are more abstract and the semantic information is more abundant, this helps to more accurately predict the target category. However, the problem of repeated detection of YOLOV3 in target detection is mainly caused by insufficient extraction of low-level feature information, resulting in inaccurate location prediction. In order to better fuse the feature information, the ADE-YOLOV3 network introduces the residual network on the 74th and 79th, 86th and 91th, 98th and 103th layers on the basis of the original network, and its network structure is as follows. Figure 3 shows.

First, the image is scaled to a uniform format of $416 \times 416 \times 3$ as a standard input for the entire network, and then features are extracted through the Darknet-53 network, in which 3×3 and 1×1 convolution layers are used continuously, 3×3 The convolutional layer is used to increase the dimension, the 1×1 convolutional layer is used to compress the 3×3 convolutional feature representation, and finally the normalization operation is added after each convolutional layer to prevent network overfitting. Then, two upsampling operations, two feature splicing operations and three residual network constant mapping operations are performed, and finally class and position prediction are performed on three scales of 13×13 , 26×26 , and 52×52 .

Figure 3: Network structure of the ADE-YOLOV3

According to the introduction and research of migration learning in [19], the trained model parameters are transferred to the new model to help the new model training, and the training effect of the new model can be improved. In this paper, the original network trained Darknet-53 network parameters are migrated to the new network structure. Figure 4 is a model training structure diagram.

Figure 4 : Vehicle detection block diagram

The specific training and detection process is:
 1. Perform 416×416 size standardization processing on the vehicle training set picture, and take the picture with uniform format as the input of the network.

2. Use the Darknet-53 network for image feature extraction.

3. Extract the output of the 74th layer and the output of the 79th layer, and perform the residual mapping operation on the two. The result is the first feature.

4. The output of the 85th layer and the output of the 61st layer are feature-spliced, and the result is mapped to the output of the 91st layer, and the result is taken as the second feature.

5. The output of the 97th layer and the output of the 36th layer are feature-spliced, and the result is mapped to the output of the 103rd layer. The result is the third feature.

6. Put the three features into the YOLO layer and train according to the set number of iterations to generate the vehicle detection weight model.

7. Input the test set image into the trained network model. The model calls the trained parameters to detect the vehicle in the test set image and output the result.

IV. EXPERIMENT AND ANALYSIS

A. Vehicle Dataset Labeling

In the process of model training, the scale and quality of the data set directly affect the effect of model training. The data source of this paper data is mainly divided into two parts: online crawling and manual shooting. Among them, online crawling data is the mainstay, supplemented by manual shooting data. The collected 1000 photos were produced according to the format of the VOC2007 data set, and the data set was divided into a training set and a test set in a ratio of 7:3. Use the labellmg image tagging tool to manually mark the target image of the training set image, as shown in Figure 5, and generate an xml file corresponding to the tag information with the target frame.

Fig.5: Labeling manual marker target box

B. Experimental Environment Configuration and Model Training Results

The experimental environment configuration is shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Environment configuration

Name	Related configuration
Central processor memory	intel(R)-CPU-E5-2620-V4, 64G
GPU	2×Nvidia TitanX
GPU acceleration library	CUDA9.0, CUDNN7.0.3
Data processing	Python, Opencv
Deep learning framework	Darknet-53

To prevent overfitting and speed up the training of the model, the momentum parameter in the network configuration parameters is set to 0.9, the weight attenuation coefficient is set to 0.0005, and the initial learning rate is set to 0.001.

C. Performance Comparison

Experiments were carried out on the same vehicle training set using the ADE-YOLOV3 network with the K-means clustering algorithm to optimize the anchor parameters, the original YOLOV3 network, and the Faster R-CNN network.

The vehicles in the 300 images in the test set are detected using the finally generated model weight file, and the average detection time, mAP value and repeated detection rate are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Comparison of test performance of different network structures

Network	Average detection time	mAP	Repeated detection rate
Faster R-CNN	0.076s	89.8%	4.5%
YOLOV3	0.019s	91.4%	5.6%
ADE-YOLOV3	0.021s	95%	2.1%

The detection contrast effect of a single image in different networks is shown in FIGS. 6 and 7.

Figure 6: YOLOV3 detection effect Figure 7 :ADE-YOLOV3 detection effect

As shown in Table 2 and Figure 6 and Figure 7, ADE-YOLOV3 has a 3.6% increase in mAP value, a 3.5% reduction in repeated detection rate, and a test speed of 50fps compared to the original network. This improves detection accuracy and effectively avoids the problem of repeated detection.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper proposes a vehicle detection method based on improved YOLOV3, called ADE-YOLOV3. The method uses K-means clustering algorithm to perform cluster analysis on its own data set, resets the anchor parameters according to the results obtained by clustering, and improves the network structure by means of migration learning. The experimental results show that compared with the original YOLOV3 method, the mAP is increased from 91.4% to 95%, the repeated detection rate is reduced from 5.6% to 2.1%, and the test speed is up to 50fps. While ensuring higher detection accuracy and faster detection speed, the problem of repeated detection is effectively avoided. For the case of errors in the detection, the next step is to further improve the way of expanding the dataset and optimizing the network structure and model parameters. At the same time, our vehicle detection is for the image dataset, and the next research direction is to focus on the video dataset. The vehicle performs fast and accurate dynamic tracking and detection.

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